

Actions for instituting gender equality & equity in landfill waste picking of Lagos State, Nigeria.

Key Highlights

- Gender-based discrimination induces violence against women landfill waste pickers of Lagos and reduces their economic opportunities.
- Key stakeholders and their roles towards instituting gender equity in landfill waste picking were identified.
- The Federal Ministry of Environment and the Lagos State Ministry of Environment & Water Resources can build on the National Policy on Solid Waste Management (2020) to develop and domesticate gender-mainstreaming strategies in the solid waste sector, particularly the landfill (informal) recycling context.
- The International Alliance of Waste Pickers can review its definition of 'waste pickers', recognising the hierarchical categorisation of the informal waste value chain.

Gender-based discrimination against women landfill waste pickers in Lagos state, Nigeria

Waste picking at landfills or government-approved dumpsites is underlaid with multiple patterns of discrimination against women. This replicates the wider patterns of inequality surrounding men-women interrelationships in society, which are reinforced by culture and religion (Mite, 2025).

At Lagos landfills, waste-picking rules are made and enforced in ways that partly or totally exclude women from available economic opportunities. Precisely, where women are given access to only nylon (flimsy plastic bags) and sacks, the two lowest-priced materials, men have legitimate access to plastic bottles, hard plastics, copper, iron, aluminium and any other thing they want. Where such picking rules are not enforced, both genders compete fiercely, and women can rarely access a reasonable volume of materials. When physical assaults result from such altercations, women become intimidated and quit picking to buy from men instead of picking freely or surviving on the few they can pick if they cannot afford to buy. These issues are reinforced by a variety of barriers. (See figure 1):

Figure 1: Barriers reinforcing gender inequality in Lagos State, Nigeria's landfill waste picking. Issues shaded in blue occur at landfill sites. Purple-shaded issue occurs in associations outside the landfill. Rose-shaded issues are societal. Each is concisely explained in the ensuing section.

For example, discrimination against women is enabled by factors centred around the physicality of waste picking (reliance on physical strength, where men have more advantage over women). Hence, men who constituted a dominant group by number and social hierarchy easily adopted dangerous picking behaviours such as rushing after moving trucks and the use of violence.

These tensions will worsen given the current economic climate of Nigeria, ridden by recession, high cost of living, internal conflicts, displacement of people and high rural-urban migration rates. In these struggles, we cannot overlook the poor and most vulnerable groups with no alternative sources of survival or access to decent jobs.

Policy landscape and the positionality of critical stakeholders on gender mainstreaming in solid waste management

The Nigerian National Gender Policy (Federal Ministry of Women and Gender Affairs, 2021) operates on three core principles- gender equality, empowerment of women, social inclusion and specifically aims *"To build a just society devoid of discrimination, where the needs and concerns of women, men, girls, boys, and other vulnerable groups are mainstreamed equitably into all sectors of national development"* (pg. 19). This is similar to the gender

mainstreaming principles given on pages 81 and 82 of the Nigerian National Policy on Solid Waste Management (2020).

The existence and relevance of waste pickers for material recovery and recycling cannot be denied, given that landfilling is a primary solid waste disposal method in Nigeria¹. This is because waste picking fits into the National Solid Waste policy's recognition of available economic opportunities from waste resources in the global economy² and facilitates the additional values of repair, reuse and recycling. Mainstreaming gender into solid waste works³ ought to apply in informal recycling contexts, where many people are employed, particularly at landfills, where men and women share a common contested space. Women working in this context ought to be protected by these laws without their informal status standing as a barrier, since they doubly qualify as a vulnerable group, being women and waste pickers.

Currently, the Lagos State Ministry of Environment & Water Resources (the apex agency formulating and domesticating federal environmental policies into Lagos State environmental laws) does not adopt a gender perspective in its policy framing. Likewise, other arms of the ministry, such as the Lagos Waste Management Authority responsible for solid waste evacuation and landfill management. Similarly, the Federal environmental ministries domiciled in Lagos State also adopt this neutral approach, which trickles down to the Local Governance level.

Thus, there is an across-the-board gender neutrality in policy formulation and execution evident in the lack of detailed attention to the role or profile of waste pickers or informal recyclers in national policy documents, besides merely mentioning them as critical stakeholders for transitioning into the circular economy in a few instances (Nigeria National Plastic Action Partnership, 2023; Ezeudu et al., 2024), and their lack of direct engagement with policy actors during policy dialogue, unlike formal waste actors. This largely affects informal recycling contexts, especially landfill sites, where women's rights are not protected.

On the other hand, where waste pickers are recognised by Non-Governmental Organisations such as the International Alliance of Waste Pickers (IAWP), they are often represented by dominant upper chain actors (such as more educated and established women and men informal aggregators) who belong to waste pickers associations with international linkages. This is largely because all informal recyclers are categorised as waste pickers by the IAWP, leading to the unintended consequence of misrepresentation and undue profiteering, and exclusion of bottom chain actors/the real needy groups (waste pickers). This also obscures their visibility and chances of accessing resources for capacity building and upward mobility in the waste value chain, especially the women landfill waste pickers who work in a secluded environment.

Using various sources of data, including interviews and literature, a map was designed to show nine stakeholders who can facilitate gender mainstreaming in landfill waste picking. How they can collaborate has been identified in a map (see Figure 2), and for these identified stakeholders, recommendations have been developed.

¹ This can be found in the Nigeria National policy on Solid Waste Management (2020), pg. 59, item 5 sub-titled '*National Waste Management Resource Action Program*).

² See pg. 57, iv, named recycle of the policy

³ See Pg. 69, item V of the National policy on Solid Waste Management (2020)

Figure 2. Ideal stakeholder interaction model for mainstreaming gender in Lagos State landfill waste picking. The yellow triangular shapes represent organisations involved in waste management and with workers waste workers at various levels. The circular blue shapes represent informal recyclers at landfills. The abbreviations used in the map are fully explained under the acronym section. More about this map here <https://kumu.io/Flobby/stakeholder-map-for-gender-mainstreaming-in-landfill-waste-picking>

Recommendations

Issues	Actors	Recommendations
Gender waste division		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Occurs when men are granted legitimate rights over higher-value materials, while women are compensated with fewer, lower-value materials. This makes men’s labour more valuable than women’s, lowering women’s income and financial capacity. 	Lagos Waste Management Authority (LAWMA) Association Leaders of Landfill Waste Pickers (ALLWP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LAWMA could mediate by teaming up with the ALLWP to revise gendered waste-picking rules and restore free access to all lucrative materials, enabling women to exercise their legitimate right to pick whatever they like.
Inequitable picking frames		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allowing men and women to pick at the same time and in the same space leads to inequity, since they comprise diverse age groups, with younger men being more energetic and physically powerful. While younger women are physically stronger than older women, both are less physically powerful than men and cannot compete on equal levels. 	LAWMA ALLWP Lagos State Ministry of Environment and Water Resources (LMEnvWR) LG Law enforcement agents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Considering the physicality of waste-picking and strength disparities between men and women, separate picking spaces can be allocated to each. Additional machines can be provided by LAWMA or LMEnvWR to facilitate this process. If this is achieved, it should be monitored to ensure fairness and equality in the kinds of materials that are dumped for both genders. Alternatively, different picking times can be allocated to both genders by the ALLWP. Both projects can be monitored periodically, enforced and sustained by the ALLWP, LG and law enforcement agents to ensure they are sustained.

Physical Violence

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> When men assert their rights over higher-value waste using force and bodily assault against women. 	<p>Local Government (LG)</p> <p>Law Enforcement Agents (e.g. police)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The LG and law enforcement agents can collaborate to ensure women's protection from all forms of violence in landfill sites. Errant men or parties should be brought under control through lawful means, and women's protection guaranteed to enable them to work freely and safely, irrespective of their lesser number.
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Low awareness of gender biases

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> When some women and most men pickers, lack consciousness of obvious practices that are biased against women and their implications. Hence, meaningful attitudinal and behavioural change cannot be attained. 	<p>NGOs</p> <p>CBOs (Community-based Organisations)</p> <p>LMEnvWR</p> <p>LAWMA</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Landfill waste pickers can be educated and sensitised on gender inequality/equity & ways to identify gender biases in their work life. Lessons should help them to develop empathy and critical reflection rather than normalising biases. Leaders in the Lagos state environmental agencies can be trained on gender sensitivity and awareness to enable them to tackle gender-based discrimination at landfills & in the waste sector impactfully.
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Dominance of upper chain actors in international representations

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Occurs when mainly the upper-class members (men & women aggregators) of frontline waste pickers associations get successfully elected into leadership, regional & international representations due to their privileges of better education, communication skills & ability to sponsor and attend the association programmes. Waste pickers, especially women, remain in the background on the grounds of low participation, reliance on daily income, inability to find time, poor communication & language skills. Prioritising only the upper-class members defeats the goal of inclusivity & empowerment of especially women waste pickers, more needy of leadership skills & resources for scaling their business. 	<p>International Alliance of Waste Pickers (IAWP)</p> <p>Frontline Waste Pickers Associations (FWPA)</p> <p>This refers to internationally affiliated associations of waste pickers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The IAWP can ensure the mandatory inclusion of women landfill waste pickers in their organising programmes with FWPA in Lagos State through dedicated enlightenment and provision of stipends to enable them to forgo daily income and attend meetings when necessary. Such programmes should prioritise engaging directly with women waste pickers at landfills and on the streets, researching extensively to understand their contextual needs and differences from other higher chain informal actors, and improving their capacity for leadership and higher roles through mentorship. There is also a need for the IAWP to review its definition of waste pickers by considering hierarchical roles in the informal waste chain, to identify and support the bottom-level actors (the waste pickers). Having women in the leadership of FWPA is not just enough. They should be trained on the fundamental principles of gender equality, equity and empathy towards (poorer) women's needs, to avoid replicating patriarchal tendencies of dominance towards less powerful groups.
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Gendered leadership structures

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In landfill waste pickers' associations, women are poorly represented, often occupying only welfare positions where they only play care-giving roles. They cannot make agentic decisions concerning women's collective working conditions as a result. 	<p>Local Government</p> <p>NGOs/CBOs</p> <p>Association Leaders of Landfill Waste Pickers (ALLWP)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The LG can partner with NGOs and CBOs in conducting gender sensitisation campaigns with the ALLWP. Including women in powerful leadership positions in landfill waste pickers associations can be prioritised, without relegating them to only catering positions, to enable them to negotiate their unique needs and be heard.
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- Women leaders should be trained to be sensitive to gender-based discrimination to avoid replicating unfair treatment against less powerful women.

Gender neutral policies

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender principles are yet to be mainstreamed in the solid waste sector of Lagos State despite existing provisions in the two aforementioned national policy documents, especially the National Policy of Solid Waste Management (2020). • This is visible in the absence of a gender perspective and practice in many environmental policy documents of the State. • Thus, women who are working in precarious and male-dominated contexts cannot easily find legal protection. | <p>Federal Ministry of Environment (FMEnv)</p> <p>LMEEnvWR</p> <p>LAWMA</p> | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The FMEnv can develop gender mainstreaming strategies in landfill waste picking, sensitise waste workers, including LAWMA staff, and landfill waste workers on gender equality and responsiveness. These strategies can be domesticated by the LMEEnvWR. • Leaders in the Lagos State solid waste agencies can be trained on gender issues in waste management and their roles in fostering gender equity/equality among waste workers, such as landfill waste pickers, when necessary. • Where few exist, more women leaders can be employed and trained on this mandate, given their better inclination to notice women’s specific needs that can be easily ignored by men. • LAWMA officials can instill and enforce egalitarian work ethics and mutual respect among men and women landfill waste pickers. When implemented, these strategies can be monitored consistently until they become routine practices. |
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Patriarchal hegemony

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bigger societal values, like male dominance and women’s subservience, are replicated in smaller contexts like landfill sites. • This is evident in men’s gate-keeping of access to valuable waste materials, male-dominated leadership, aggressive behaviour, higher income opportunities and women’s calculated silence, lack of agency, voice and unwilling acceptance of gendered rules. | <p>Lagos State Ministry of Environment and Water Resources (LMEEnvWR)</p> <p>Local Government (LG)</p> <p>NGOs / CBOs</p> | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Periodic training of all actors at landfills on gender equity/equality can be conducted urgently and separately for the ALLWP, LAWMA staff, men & women waste pickers by the NGOs/CBOs in partnership with the LMEEnvWR or the LG. • They can be sensitised on the importance of empowering women to thrive as independent adults and equal co-workers, not as subordinates of male colleagues. • Women waste pickers can be enlightened on refusing the burdens of patriarchal hegemony in workspaces. Otherwise, they will continue suffering exclusion, and widows, unmarried women, and married women whose husbands do not work in this space will suffer more since their exclusion would mean total cut off from economic opportunities and income for their household. |
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Acronyms

ALLWP	Association Leaders of Landfill Waste Pickers
CBOs	Community-based Organisations
FMEEnv	Federal Ministry of Environment
IAWP	International Alliance of Waste Pickers
LAWMA	Lagos Waste Management Authority
LG	Local Government
LWP	Landfill waste pickers
LMEnvWR	Lagos State Ministry of Environment and Water Resources
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
WP	Waste pickers